

What Makes a Good City? Exploring Young People's Experiences of Urban Nature

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Version Control Notice

This report shares early findings from continuing research that is currently undergoing academic peer review. This report has been made publicly available to support timely access for practitioners and policymakers.

The findings, interpretations, and recommendations presented here are provisional and may be updated as the peer-review process progresses. Once the peer-reviewed article is published, this report will be updated and a link to the final version of record will be provided to ensure users have access to the most reliable and up-to-date evidence.

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Executive Summary

Young people have a distinct intergenerational stake in the future of the planet and in the environmental decisions shaping it. Most now live in towns and cities, where everyday opportunities for encountering nature offer important benefits but are unevenly experienced due to persistent socio-spatial inequalities. Elevating young people’s perspectives on nature today – and ensuring their meaningful participation in decision-making for the future – is essential for creating resilient, inclusive and environmentally just towns and cities.

This report summarises early findings from ‘The Good City’ project, exploring how young people experience, value, and are shaped by urban nature. Introducing participatory mapping to more than 400 young people across five secondary schools in Edinburgh, we examined their routine exposure to nature along travel routes, the nature-benefits and challenges they identify, and the opportunities they see for environmental improvements in their neighbourhoods.

Our intention is for the findings from this report to support constructive conversations with local and national policymakers, civic society, educators and young people themselves. These discussions can help identify and prioritise key themes, questions, and actions needed to develop a Living Lab grounded in the inclusive design, delivery, and co-management of Nature Networks, with a particular focus on young people.

Key Findings:

1. Young people’s routine exposure to nature during their daily commutes is primarily shaped by landscape-scale context, entrenching neighbourhood inequalities.

- 44% of participating young people travelled home from school using active modes (walking and/or cycling), covering a mean travel distance of 1.7 km.
- Greenness experienced along active travel routes was largely shaped by the surrounding landscape, limiting young people’s routine exposure to nature.
- In high-green landscapes, active travel routes were consistently less green than their wider surroundings.
- Gender and cultural background influenced exposure to nature during active travel, though small samples for minority groups limit interpretation.

2. Young people recognise diverse benefits of nature in their neighbourhoods – but individual and demographic factors influence their ability to accrue and share that knowledge.

- 64% of participating young people mapped places that were ‘good for wildlife’ describing an average of two broad taxonomic groups each (e.g. birds, mammals, plants).
- 42% mapped places where they could ‘get things from nature’, describing natural resources for play, decoration and also wild food.
- Young people were almost three times as likely to map natural places that were important to them (45%) compared to those that bothered them (17%).
- Self-reported nature connection, gender and cultural background were strongly associated with young people’s ability to map positive natural places.
- Socioeconomic background influenced young people’s ability to identify natural places that bothered them.

3. Young people clearly identify environmental challenges within the urban environment, prioritising cultural and supporting aspects of nature alongside regulating and provisioning ecosystem services.

- 60% of participating young people mapped at least one location in the city that they felt needed improvement.
- Noise was the most frequently mapped issue (43% participants), followed by aesthetics (34%), air quality (31%), flooding (26%), water quality (18%) and overheating (14%).
- Environmental, demographic and individual factors did not appear to influence young people's ability to identify places needing improvements.

Recommendations for inclusive Nature Networks:

- ❖ **Prioritise improvements in nature-poor neighbourhoods.** Edinburgh's least green neighbourhoods are clustered together in densely populated central and coastal zones. Targeted improvements in these areas would yield the greatest benefits for all residents, and particularly young people travelling to and from school who have limited opportunities to improve their daily exposure to nature.
- ❖ **Recognise and respond to the full spectrum of young people's experience in participatory engagement.** Meaningful participation needs to actively involve young people across the full spectrum of nature connection, apply gender-sensitive design and ensure representation from diverse cultural backgrounds and the most deprived neighbourhoods.
- ❖ **Elevate cultural ecosystem services.** Young people value nature's contributions to aesthetics, recreation and mental and physical wellbeing as well as provision of resources for decoration and play. Integrating these cultural dimensions more fully into Nature Network framing would better align policy with the lived experiences and priorities of young people.

Conclusions:

Young people in Edinburgh bring deep and nuanced knowledge of their urban environments. Their daily experiences of nature are shaped more by structural landscape features than by demographic or individual characteristics, yet their values, priorities, and sensitivities vary widely. Spatial planning that incorporates this diversity can support greener, healthier and more equitable cities. If co-designed with young people, Scotland's Nature Networks offer a powerful opportunity to reshape young people's everyday relationships with urban nature and deliver benefits for future generations.

Future work should aim for inclusion of young people across the full socio-economic spectrum, while considering the impacts of disability, mobility, the experiences of young people not attending mainstream school settings and the ways that young people encounter and value blue spaces.

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1. Introduction

Current trajectories of nature loss and climate change – unless reversed – will fall disproportionately on today’s younger generations, giving them a distinct intergenerational stake in the state of their environment. Young people today primarily encounter nature within the towns and cities where they live (Chawla 2015; Olcese et al. 2026), a shift driven by rapid global urbanisation. These everyday encounters are not experienced equally: socio-spatial inequalities shape both the quality and accessibility of urban nature, influencing young people’s opportunities to develop meaningful connections with nature and enjoy the benefits of improved environmental health, physical and mental wellbeing, place-making and cultural identity.

Despite significant short- and long-term implications of environmental change for young people, institutional, procedural and cultural barriers continue to restrict their ability to influence spatial planning and environmental decision-making (Hagemann et al. 2024; Jaffe and Loebach 2024; Pia and Bezboruah 2025). This apparent disconnect between young people’s lived experiences of nature and their limited opportunities to shape environmental decisions highlights a persistent problem of marginalisation and environmental injustice. Elevating their perspectives and participation is therefore essential for creating resilient, inclusive and environmentally just towns and cities.

In this report we explore existing evidence on how young people interact with urban nature, the specific context for young people growing up in Scotland and the national policy landscape, with a particular focus on Nature Networks as an environmental and spatial planning tool. We then introduce our research – engaging over 400 young people (age 12-18) in Edinburgh in a participatory mapping exercise – and make recommendations for more inclusive environmental planning in Scotland’s towns and cities.

1.1 Young people and nature

Regular contact with nature, and a sense of connection, supports young people’s mental wellbeing, cognitive development, physical health, social engagement, environmental identity and stewardship and sense of place (Jack 2010; Chawla 2015; Alderton et al. 2019; Madera et al. 2024). Early experiences with *everyday nature* – safe, welcoming, culturally relevant, and socially meaningful – can foster pro-environmental values that endure long beyond childhood (Madera et al. 2024), especially when young people are empowered within participatory environmental decision-making (Olcese et al. 2026).

However, specific barriers influence how young people navigate their environments and the quality of their interactions with nature. These barriers include declining leisure time, digitalisation, cultural concerns around safety and limited independent mobility (Jack 2010; Chawla 2015; Madera et al. 2024; Waite et al. 2023). A substantial body of research now describes a decline in frequent, direct nature encounters among young people – an “extinction of experience” that is increasingly urban in character and particularly associated with adolescence (Chawla 2020; Van Heel et al. 2023; Madera et al. 2024; M. Richardson et al. 2019; Miller 2005).

Alongside these barriers, structural inequalities related to land use and housing (Das 2025), gender (Cole et al. 2024; Collins et al. 2025; Bornioli et al. 2024), cultural, ethnic and racial identity (Roberts et al. 2021; Collins et al. 2025; Das 2025), disability (Horton 2017; Lieberman et al. 2023; Schmidt 2023), immigration (Gentin et al. 2019) and socioeconomics (Das 2025; Newton et al. 2026) shape where urban nature is found and who can access it.

For example, a recent analysis of large European cities found that those offering good walkability for young people’s journeys to and from school often exhibited lower levels of greenness, highlighting a clear trade-off between accessibility and environmental quality (Willberg et al. 2024). Together, these spatial and social constraints create marked differences in nature provision, experience and connection between individuals, communities, cities and regions (Das 2025; Newton et al. 2026; Sun et al. 2022).

“Finding ways to bring nature to children, even in densely populated and low resourced parts of the world, appears essential to foster connection. Doing this can simultaneously create networks of green spaces for biodiversity and offer many opportunities for children to become involved in nature protection and restoration.” – Chawla 2020

1.2 Growing up in Scotland

According to the 2023 *State of Nature* report, Scotland has experienced globally significant declines in habitats and species due to human activities, reducing the capacity of ecosystems to deliver vital benefits to people (Burns et al. 2023). A recent NatureScot report ‘*Understanding the Indirect Drivers of Biodiversity Loss in Scotland*’ highlights that urbanisation – driven by overall population growth and rural-urban migration of predominately young adults – is contributing to biodiversity loss in Scotland, especially across the central urban belt (Pakeman et al. 2023). Over 80% of Scotland’s population is urban (Scottish Government 2021), and more than 20% live within the two largest cities alone (National Records of Scotland 2024).

Evidence from across Scotland shows that children and young people experience nature in diverse ways. Patterns of activity, wellbeing and health show clear socioeconomic and urban–rural inequalities that are likely to impact young people’s ability to form strong connections with nature, and/or enjoy the benefits nature provides. Young people from urban, low-income households spend less time being active and less time outdoors than those from rural or high-income households (Olsen et al. 2021; McCrorie et al. 2020; Olsen et al. 2022). Environmental satisfaction is lower among disabled young people and those living in the most deprived areas, with the latter also less likely to be satisfied with their health (Knudsen et al. 2025). Accessible, local natural spaces support children’s social and emotional wellbeing, with larger relative benefits observed for low-income families (Olsen et al. 2021; E. A. Richardson et al. 2017; Aggio et al. 2015). And children’s health-related quality of life — particularly self-esteem — is associated with use of greenspace, rather than simply the *amount* of greenspace nearby (McCracken et al. 2016).

Outdoor public and natural spaces are recognised as important settings for children and young people in Scotland to meet friends, play, form identities, test boundaries and gain independence from family and school; however, lack of variety limits opportunities for play and exploration, and teenagers are often exposed to ambivalent or negative attitudes from adults concerning their use of these spaces (Day & Wager 2010; Bell 2003). Improving access to urban greenspace for young people needs more than physical amenities; it requires recognition of how existing community contexts, specifically social cohesion, shape who gets to meaningfully access and benefit from these spaces (Seaman 2010).

Taken together, these previous studies show that young people’s exposure to, and engagement with, urban nature in Scotland is shaped by a combination of environmental,

socio-demographic, cultural and neighbourhood contexts, while recognising that evidence on the impacts of gender, disability and racial, ethnic and cultural identity is largely missing.

1.3 The policy landscape for urban nature and people

Major international frameworks – such as the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (2022–2030), UNFCCC Glasgow Climate Pact (2021) and the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (2015)– now explicitly endorse integrated environmental and social governance, emphasizing the interdependence of human wellbeing, biodiversity, and climate stability. In Scotland, a growing body of national and regional policy seeks to operationalize these global ambitions, including the Environment Strategy for Scotland (2021), the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy to 2045, Scotland’s Draft Climate Change Plan 2026-2040, Scottish National Adaptation Plan 2024–2029, and National Planning Framework 4. Recent legislative developments – such as the UNCRC (Incorporation) (Scotland) Act 2024 and the Natural Environment (Scotland) Bill (2025) – signal a national shift toward a more rights-based and statutorily binding approach to environmental and social governance.

Nature Networks have become a central element of Scotland’s approach to spatial and environmental planning, building on the priority species and habitats guidance contained within Local Biodiversity Action Plans. The *Nature Networks Framework for Scotland* (NatureScot 2024) sets out a vision for a well-connected, ecologically representative and equitably governed system of green and blue infrastructure that supports biodiversity, ecosystem services and community wellbeing. By enabling spatial decision-making at the local authority level, Nature Networks are intended to allow tailored responses to ecological fragmentation while aligning with national targets such as the CBD’s 30x30 biodiversity commitment. The Framework emphasises codesign, participatory governance and the integration of local knowledge - key principles of inclusive, place-based planning. Diversity and inclusion are positioned as core to decision-making and delivery, adopting a ‘whole-of-society’ approach. Where there are multiple options for delivering connectivity, local knowledge and ecological conditions should drive decision-making.

“By 2030 Scotland will have evolving, flexible and resilient Nature Networks connecting nature-rich areas allowing wildlife and natural processes to move and adapt to land use and climate change pressures. The networks will help build people’s connection to nature, providing biodiversity-rich spaces that deliver local benefits, and meet the priorities of local communities for nature.” –The Nature Networks Framework for Scotland (NatureScot 2024)

While the primary purpose of Nature Networks is to improve ecological connectivity, the Framework strongly emphasises the provision of ecosystem services, and a mechanism for mainstreaming and delivering the benefits of biodiversity to people, especially those in urban environments (NatureScot 2024). Ecosystem services are a scientific concept, encompassing the benefits provided by nature to people and society. They are commonly categorised as supporting (e.g., habitat provision, photosynthesis, soil formation), regulating (e.g. air and water purification, flood and temperature regulation, pollination), provisioning (e.g. food, raw materials and medicines) and cultural (e.g. physical and mental wellbeing, recreation and spiritual values; Stanworth et al. 2024;

NatureScot 2025a). ‘Nature’s Contributions to People’ is a similar, highly inclusive term incorporating concepts such as ecosystem goods and services, alongside those derived from indigenous knowledge systems (IPBES 2019).

*“Nature Networks are seen as a public good, providing ecosystem services such as clear air and water, as well as health and wellbeing benefits, and highlight the importance of Scotland's nature to people and the economy. They act as a vital tool to mainstream biodiversity not only in policy but throughout society and people's connection with nature. Nature Networks deliver the benefits of biodiversity for people to people's doorsteps.” - **The Nature Networks Framework for Scotland (NatureScot 2024)***

Scotland’s environmental and planning strategies are complemented by a suite of policies focused on the rights and wellbeing of children and young people, such as the UNCRC (Incorporation) (Scotland) Act 2024, the Child Poverty Act 2017, ‘Getting it Right for Every Child’, the Play Strategy 2025-2030 and the integration of outdoor learning and ‘Learning for Sustainability’ throughout the Curriculum for Excellence.

Over recent years NatureScot has emphasised the importance of young people, working to improve access to nature through its Youth Engagement Action Plan (NatureScot 2025b). In 2015, it partnered with YoungScot to establish a National Biodiversity Panel that identified ways to better support young people’s access to and engagement with nature and greenspace. This collaboration led to several targeted initiatives, including improving greenspace access in disadvantaged areas, developing nature-based skills programmes, exploring barriers faced by young women in outdoor settings, and launching the *Future Routes Fund*, which enabled young people to design and deliver their own nature-focused projects.

*“Young people are one of our key stakeholders in realising a nature-rich future. A stronger youth voice is critical to improve biodiversity loss and deliver the nature-based solutions we need to address climate change. The next generation has always challenged the prevailing consensus. They are both the current and future guardians of our environment.” - **Francesca Osowska (NatureScot Chief Executive to 2025; NatureScot 2025b)***

While Scotland offers an ambitious social and environmental policy landscape, the key test is delivery - especially in cities where socio-ecological pressures are most acute. A coalition of more than 80 organisations recently highlighted ongoing marginalisation of young people, disabled people and ethnic minority communities in environmental planning (Everyone’s Environment 2025). They identified green and blue space developments as a priority area for consistent, meaningful engagement, improved quality and accessibility, and provision of sustainable roles for communities in management and ownership.

1.4 The Edinburgh Nature Network

With a population of 523,250 in 2023, the City of Edinburgh is the second-largest city in Scotland and the fourth fastest-growing city in the UK (City of Edinburgh Council 2024).

Active and sustainable travel is common and access to nature is high, e.g. nearly 70% of trips under two miles are made on foot or by bicycle, 74% of residents live within a five-minute walk of a green or blue space and 92% report that they are satisfied with their nearest green space (City of Edinburgh Council 2024).

The Edinburgh Nature Network (ENN, 2022), together with the Edinburgh Biodiversity Action Plan (EBAP, 2022–27), provides the strategic framework for conserving, enhancing, and connecting biodiversity across the city, while delivering multiple ecosystem services (Edinburgh Living Landscapes n.d.). The ENN was developed using an adaptation of the Ecological Coherency Protocol (EcoCo 2019), integrating detailed data on habitats with information on ecosystem service capacity and demand (such as air and water purification, noise, temperature and flood regulation, health and wellbeing, and pollination).

Local knowledge and practical considerations – gathered through consultation workshops – were incorporated to identify opportunities for multi-beneficial nature-based solutions and environmental enhancements. As far as we are aware, young people’s needs, values and priorities have not yet been explicitly addressed in the development of the ENN; however, the Wilding Wee Spaces project provides opportunities to engage young people in delivery, by supporting schools to codesign ecologically rich spaces within the network (Thriving Greenspaces n.d.).

1.5 This study

The 2023 NatureScot report exploring indirect drivers of biodiversity loss in Scotland, highlighted low engagement with nature, unequal access to nature in deprived communities, the effects of urbanisation and technology on children’s nature connection and limited use of local knowledge and democracy deficits in land-use planning (Pakeman et al. 2023). The report called for greater opportunities for nature connection – particularly for children, young people, and urban or deprived communities – and for participatory governance that integrates local knowledge and supports complex decision-making. In this study, we respond to these priorities by focusing on people–nature connectedness (especially in urban contexts and among young people), human capital and resilience (including the role of education), and widening public participation in environmental and land-use planning.

Framing the City of Edinburgh as a case study, we examine how everyday encounters with nature on the way to and from school shape young people’s lived experiences and explore how their knowledge and values relating to nature and the urban environment can be integrated with codesigned planning tools, such as Nature Networks. This study was developed in the early 2020s in response to the impacts of the COVID 19 pandemic, rising youth climate activism, and Scotland’s strengthened commitment to children’s rights. Our work was motivated by the need to address ongoing inequalities in young people’s access to nature and to ensure that there are meaningful opportunities for young people to shape the environmental decisions that will define their future. Against this backdrop, we addressed three core research questions:

- 1) How does young people’s routine exposure to nature vary across the city?
- 2) Do young people recognise the (dis-)benefits of nature within their neighbourhoods?
- 3) Can young people identify opportunities for nature-based improvements?

2. Methods

2.1 Data collection

We used a mixed-methods approach to develop a holistic understanding of young people's urban experiences with nature. Between August 2022 and March 2023, we visited five secondary schools in Edinburgh, engaging over 400 young people through interactive presentations on urban nature and resilience. We then shared our research survey in the same session using Maptionnaire, a secure online mapping platform, with 305 young people submitting anonymous responses.

Participatory Mapping - We invited young people to map their most recent route home from school (typically the previous day) and identify locations in their neighbourhoods relevant to nature and resilience, including: 1) good places to see wildlife, 2) good places for natural resources, 3) natural places that are important to them, 4) natural places that bother them and 5) places needing improvements (e.g. due to water / air pollution, noise, overheating, flooding, poor aesthetics). Free-text answers allowed participants to describe these locations and what they experience there.

Questionnaire - We gathered data on participants' perceived connection to nature (based on the *Inclusion of Nature in Self* framework; Wesley Schultz 2001; Martin and Czellar 2016), access to household garden space, cars and bicycles, and basic demographic details (age range, gender, and cultural background). All multiple-choice categories are described in Appendix B).

Feedback - We gathered feedback using a five-point Likert scale with open text answers for comments.

Geospatial data - We approximated nature exposure using 'greenness' data derived from satellite imagery; the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) ranges from -1 to 1, with values above zero indicating the presence of vegetation, and higher values reflecting denser and healthier vegetation (higher greenness). Socioeconomic context was approximated using the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD 2020), which provides detailed spatial data on relative deprivation, ranking Scotland's data zones from 1 (most deprived) to 6,976 (least deprived).

2.4 Research ethics

Prior to research commencing, we sought approval from the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh's Research Ethics Committee (12 April 2021) and research access approval from the Community and Families Department of the City of Edinburgh Council (Ref: MG/AF 17 August 2022). Informed consent was requested from all participants, with alternative activities offered for those not wishing to participate. To preserve anonymity, we asked young people to finish mapping their travel routes at the nearest main street or ~100m from their home address. Schools are anonymised throughout the report.

Detailed methods including analyses and study limitations are presented in Appendix A.

3. Discussion

3.1 How does young people's routine exposure to nature vary across the city? (RQ1)

Our first aim was to understand how young people routinely encounter nature within their urban environments. We used their everyday journeys between school and home as a window into these lived experiences, allowing us to examine the spatial, environmental, demographic, and individual factors that contribute to - or constrain - everyday exposure to nature, without biasing participation by relying on specialist knowledge of or experiences with nature.

We focused on the journey *home* from school because early piloting indicated that young people have greater autonomy over route choice after school than in the morning. This part of the analysis was restricted to those travelling actively - walking and/or cycling - as these young people are more directly exposed to their surroundings. Forty-four percent of participants in our study reported active travel, sitting at the lower end of predicted walking accessibility for secondary schools across major European cities (Willberg et al. 2024). Active travel in our sample generally covered less distance than vehicular travel (mean = 1.7 km vs 5.7 km) and active travellers reported more positive perceptions of their route (e.g., pleasantness, sociability, safety, and speed), whereas vehicular travel was often based on necessity.

To approximate nature exposure, we used a 'greenness' vegetation index (NDVI) derived from satellite imagery. We summarised greenness within the immediate surroundings of each route (30-m buffer) to represent the nature encountered directly during travel and contrasted this with broader landscape-scale greenness (500-m buffer) and city-wide spatial patterns.

We found a strong and precise positive association between experienced travel greenness and landscape-scale greenness. Males and young people identifying with cultural backgrounds other than White or Asian appeared to travel along greener routes, although uncertainty around these estimates was high and/or interpretation was constrained due to small sample sizes. There were no meaningful relationships between travel greenness and socioeconomic deprivation, home greenness, nature connection or age (Figure 1).

The nature of the relationship between route and landscape-scale greenness indicated that while the broad landscape provides the context, it does not determine the travel greenness along a 1:1 relationship. Young people in Edinburgh generally travel through routes that are less green than their wider surroundings, a trend which is more pronounced in high greenness landscapes (NDVI >0.4).

Overall, these findings suggest that young people's routine exposure to nature as they travel through the city is not evenly distributed and is strongly shaped by the surrounding landscape, largely independent of individual characteristics or local socioeconomic context. This pattern has implications for inequality: young people travelling within nature-deprived neighbourhoods currently have limited opportunities to improve their exposure as they travel, even if they possess a strong nature connection or desire greener environments. Given that travel routes are generally in the public realm, there is a clear opportunity for improvements in street layout, tree placement, and local planting to improve access and exposure to nature during active travel. Gender and

cultural background may also present broader structural constraints on nature exposure that needs further investigation.

		RQ1 Exposure		RQ2 (Dis-)Benefits		RQ3 ES	
Response variables		Route NDVI (30m)	Route-Landscape NDVI (30m)	Positive natural locations	Wildlife taxa	Bothersome natural locations	Improvements
Nature Connection		●	●	●	●	●	●
Environmental Context	Home NDVI	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Home SIMD	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Landscape NDVI (500m)	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Route SIMD (30m)	●	●	●	●	●	●
Gender	Female vs. Male	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Non-Binary vs Male	●	●	●	●	●	●
Cultural Background	Asian vs White	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Other backgrounds vs White	●	●	●	●	●	●
Age	Age 14-16 vs 12-14	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Age 16-18 vs 12-14	●	●	●	●	●	●

Figure 1. Associations between predictors and response variables in the Bayesian hierarchical framework for each research question (1-3), showing the direction (blue = positive; orange = negative) and certainty of associations (dark = high confidence / meaningful; light = low confidence / not meaningful). RQ1 explores young people’s routine exposure to nature according to greenness experienced along their routes home from school. RQ2 addresses whether young people recognise the (dis)benefits of nature, mapping positive and bothersome natural locations and reporting wildlife taxa. RQ3 explores whether young people can identify and map places needing improvements across the city due to lack of ecosystem services (ES). NDVI = Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (satellite-derived greenness); SIMD = Scottish Index of Multiple

Our analysis of contextual greenness revealed substantial spatial clustering across Edinburgh (Figure 2). Data zones with dense concentrations of high-greenness are found in the rural western fringes of the city and pronounced areas of low-greenness in densely populated city centre and coastal areas. The relationship between greenness and social deprivation across Edinburgh is complex. At the data zone level, the most deprived neighbourhoods contained very few clusters of high-greenness, while low-greenness areas were distributed across the full spectrum of SIMD ranks. Notably, the least deprived neighbourhoods – many located near the city centre – also exhibited lower landscape-scale greenness. Our sampled schools (and most participating young people’s home environments) were drawn from areas with lower-than-average deprivation, meaning our ability to detect associations between deprivation, greenness, and route choice across the full socioeconomic range may be limited.

Detailed results for all research questions are provided in Appendix B.

Figure 2. A. Mean greenness (NDVI) for data zones across the City of Edinburgh. B. Local spatial clustering of greenness (NDVI) between data zones. Spatial clustering was identified using Local Moran's I, classifying each data zone into clusters of high-greenness (HH), low-greenness (LL) and high-low or low-high boundary zones (HL or LH) based on mean weighted NDVI.

3.2 Do young people recognise the (dis)benefits of nature within their neighbourhoods? (RQ2)

Having established young people's baseline exposure to nature - and the structural factors that shape it - we then sought to understand how they themselves perceive the role of nature in their neighbourhoods. We were interested not only in *what* natural features young people notice, but also in their taxonomic awareness, how they use local nature as a resource, and the ways in which nature contributes positively to (or detracts from) their daily lives.

To explore this local knowledge, we asked young people to map locations that they were familiar with, and to provide additional information about the types of natural places they encounter, how they experience them, and why these places matter. This approach allowed us to capture the richness of young people's place-based expertise and to identify both the benefits they associate with nature and the aspects they find challenging or problematic.

Places considered 'good for wildlife' were the most mapped natural features in our study, with almost two-thirds of participants responding to this question, identifying an average of 1.3 places each. In contrast, fewer than half of participants mapped places where they could 'get things from nature' and they mapped fewer sites overall (mean = 0.5 locations per participant). Participants were around three times more likely to map natural places that were important to them (45% participants responded, mean = 0.7 locations per participant) than places that bothered them (17% participants responded, mean = 0.2 locations per participant). The relative popularity of these categories may indicate that young people hold more positive than negative feelings about nature in the city, or that they are more accustomed to expressing positive views.

In our modelling, clear individual and demographic patterns emerged: self-reported nature connection, gender and cultural background were strong correlates of young people's ability or willingness to map natural places in their neighbourhoods (Figure 1). The more connected to nature an individual felt, the more likely they were to identify positive natural places, and to report a greater diversity of wildlife taxa. By contrast, nature connection had no impact on an individual's likelihood of mapping natural places that bothered them, indicating a strong positive knowledge of or relationship with natural places, rather than a greater overall willingness to participate in the survey.

Females identified more positive natural places than males, and they also reported a greater diversity of wildlife taxa. However, there was no gender differences in mapping natural places that bothered participants. Some differences in mapping of natural places emerged across cultural backgrounds. For example, young people that identified with Asian and other cultural backgrounds, mapped fewer positive natural locations than young people from White backgrounds.

The greenness and socio-economic context of young people's home and travel environments and their age group did not appear to influence mapping of positive natural spaces or wildlife taxa in a meaningful way. However, the SIMD rank of a young person's home environment positively associated with their likelihood of mapping natural places that bothered them, indicating that young people from the most deprived neighbourhoods are less likely to identify negative natural encounters and *vice versa*. This pattern could be reflective of differences in perspective or attitudes to nature along this socioeconomic spectrum, or knowledge and experience of natural locations outside their daily commutes.

Wildlife locations and taxonomic richness - The wildlife locations mapped by participants included descriptions of green features (n=217) alongside blue (n=93) and grey features (n=41). Young people who mapped places for wildlife were, on average, able to describe two broad taxonomic groups associated with these locations. Some listed up to seven, often providing additional details such as common names for species and behavioural observations. Birds, mammals and plants were mentioned most frequently, while invertebrates, fish, amphibians and fungi were referenced far less often.

'Huge trees, beautiful leaves, nice place to play football. Squirrels, bugs, crows, lady bugs, pigeon, etc' - MALE, AGE 14-16

'There are lots of hedges and trees and it is quite peaceful as there is not much traffic. Wood pigeons, starlings, blackbirds and robins. The starlings' nest on the church spire. In the summer there are swifts. I also see grey squirrels.' - FEMALE, AGE 12-14

Nature as a resource – Descriptions of locations where young people get things from nature referenced primarily green features (n = 81), followed by grey (n = 18) and blue features (n = 17). When describing what they obtained from nature at these sites, young people mentioned natural resources for play and decoration (e.g., conkers, seashells, sticks, feathers) and wild foods (e.g., berries and tree nuts). Others described gaining restorative experiences or taking photos, suggest a cultural and relational connection to nature in the city environment.

'Conkers especially when there are loads it's fun breaking them open and I take them home, put them in a bowl, they look really nice.' - FEMALE, AGE 12-14

Greenery along the canal. Elderflower rosehip and blackberries. - MALE, AGE 14-16

Important natural places and those that bother young people – Important natural places mapped by young people primarily included descriptions of green features (n = 104), followed by grey (n = 20) and blue features (n = 19). Popular reasons provided for why young people found these natural places important included: beauty and/or inspiration, leisure, mental and physical health benefits. Others described natural places as having social value among their friends and families or sentimental and nostalgic value, especially related to childhood experiences.

'It lets me breathe and get my anger out.' - FEMALE, AGE 12-14

In contrast, reasons given for why some natural places bothered young people, included perceptions of dirt and/or litter, safety concerns and dislike at getting muddy, stung or ‘jagged’. In this category, most descriptions included green (n = 22) and grey features (n = 15) with few blue features (n = 2).

“Green field in middle of neighbourhood. Bare, big uncontrollable dogs run around off lead.” – MALE, AGE 12-14

3.3 Can young people identify ecosystem dis-services and opportunities for nature-based improvements? (RQ3)

Sixty percent of participants in our survey mapped at least one location in the city that they felt needed improvement. The most frequently reported issues included places that were too noisy (reported by 43% participants), too ugly (34%) or suffer from poor air quality (31%), followed by issues such as flooding (26%), poor water quality (18%) and overheating (14%). In an open category, 20% participants highlighted locations needing improvements due to other reasons, such as insufficient or poor quality nature or greenspace, anthropogenic waste (e.g. litter, fly tipping), traffic and road issues, safety concerns, unpleasant smells, being too busy or too dark, references to particular neighbourhoods and infrastructure (e.g. schools and housing), poor accessibility, and a lack of facilities including shops and phone signal.

Unlike our findings for natural places, mapping rates for locations needing improvements across the city showed no associations with environmental, demographic or individual factors. This supports the conclusion that the links between nature connection, gender, and cultural background in mapping the (dis)benefits of nature are genuine, rather than a methodological artefact such as willingness to participate.

Among young people in our sample, the cultural service of aesthetic value – including landscape quality and a sense of beauty – emerged as a frequently mapped issue, second only to noise. This indicates that cultural ecosystem services are not peripheral: they are central to how young people understand and evaluate their neighbourhoods.

Across the survey, young people demonstrated a rich awareness of a broad range of ecosystem services. As reported earlier: 64% of participants mapped places that were ‘good for wildlife,’ reflecting recognition of supporting services; 42% identified places where they could ‘get things from nature,’ indicating awareness of provisioning and cultural services; and 45% mapped places important for aesthetic value, leisure, or health, capturing a range of cultural services. These results suggest that young people hold a multidimensional understanding of nature in their environments – one that spans the full ecosystem services spectrum, not only the regulating services often emphasised in current policy framing. Integrating these perspectives more explicitly into urban nature planning could help ensure that future decision-making more fully reflects the everyday needs, values, and priorities of the young people who live there.

3.4 What did we learn about urban young people?

Self-reported nature connection was a consistent predictor of young people’s ability and/or willingness to identify positive natural locations and report wildlife, but it had

little influence on perceptions of negative natural spaces, places needing improvement, or the measured greenness of their chosen travel routes. Although Edinburgh contains some of the most and least deprived areas in Scotland (City of Edinburgh Council 2020), the only clear association in our data was that young people from deprived neighbourhoods were less likely to identify natural places that bothered them, and *vice versa*. As our sample underrepresented school catchments from the most deprived areas, further work is needed to understand experiences of young people from Edinburgh's most deprived neighbourhoods and from other Scottish towns and cities with different socioeconomic contexts.

Demographic factors also shaped how young people perceived and navigated urban nature. Cultural background influenced the ability to recognise both benefits and disbenefits of urban nature, though interpretation is challenged by small sample sizes meaning that the drivers of these differences remain unclear. Gender emerged as a strong predictor of identifying positive natural places, but gender differences disappeared for negative places or those needing improvement. No meaningful age differences were found within the 12–18 range, offering a baseline for understanding the nature experiences of young people in Edinburgh and supporting future comparisons across time and across Scotland.

3.5 What did we learn for inclusive, participatory Nature Networks?

Young people's inclusion in urban nature planning must recognise the diversity within this group, acknowledging differences in personality, socioeconomic background, gender and cultural background rather than assuming they hold a single, uniform set of priorities. A young person's personal connection to nature also influences how they experience and evaluate urban nature, meaning participatory design processes need to account for this variation to avoid overrepresenting the perspectives of those who are already highly connected to nature.

Current framing of Nature Networks places a strong emphasis on supporting and regulating services such as habitat creation, nature restoration, flood mitigation, and improvements to air and water quality (NatureScot 2024). Our findings suggest that young people may be especially motivated by nature-based improvements that enhance cultural and supporting services, and among regulating services they prioritise actions to reduce noise and improve aesthetics, with secondary interest in addressing air and water quality and flooding, and little immediate concern about overheating. These data provide an important baseline to monitor the attitudes of young people and help Nature Networks to deliver local benefits and meet the priorities of local communities for nature.

Finally, we must recognise that opportunities identified in Nature Network planning are likely to have real-world consequences for urban residents. Decisions about which improvements are implemented, and in which neighbourhoods, matter greatly: for example investment in high quality greenspace in socioeconomic and nature-deprived areas can deliver disproportionately positive outcomes for disadvantaged children, while greenspace concentrated in affluent areas or within private ownership risks reinforcing existing inequalities (Newton et al. 2026).

4. Conclusion

Towns and cities remain socially, spatially and ecologically dynamic, offering significant potential to transform how young people experience and benefit from nature. Yet longstanding inequalities continue to shape who gains access to high quality greenspace, where health and wellbeing benefits accrue and who gets to be involved with decision-making. Against this backdrop, a question arises of not only what a Nature Network designed with young people in mind would look like, but also how their full inclusion in environmental and spatial planning and delivery might reshape both the distribution of benefits and their own relationships with urban nature.

Our research shows that Edinburgh's young people hold diverse experiences, knowledge and priorities related to nature. Routine exposure to nature during active travel is determined primarily by landscape context, meaning that young people from nature-deprived areas have few opportunities to enhance their experiences of nature in their everyday movements around the city. Nature connection strongly influences their ability or willingness to identify positive natural places and report wildlife, but has little impact on recognising negative spaces, improvement needs, or the greenness of daily travel routes. Socioeconomic context introduces further complexity: the only clear association we found is that young people from more deprived neighbourhoods are less likely to identify natural sites that bother them, and *vice versa*. The underrepresentation of participants from the most deprived areas in our sample highlights the need for targeted research both within Edinburgh and across Scotland's towns and cities, where socioeconomic conditions differ substantially. Demographic factors also play an important role, with cultural background shaping recognition of nature's benefits and disbenefits, and females identifying more positive natural places than males. These patterns reflect wider patterns while emphasising social and structural barriers that continue to limit equitable access to greenspace for Scotland's young people.

Taken together, our findings underscore the need for urban nature planning that meaningfully accounts for the diversity of young people's identities, priorities and lived experiences. Participatory design processes must avoid assuming homogeneity and remain attentive to how factors such as nature connection, socioeconomics, cultural background and gender shape young people's interactions with urban nature. Within Scotland's Nature Network framework, the current emphasis on supporting and regulating services – such as habitat creation and environmental regulatory services – risks overlooking other functions and services that young people may value most. Evidence from this report shows that young people are particularly motivated by improvements that enhance cultural and supporting services, as well as specific regulating services such as reducing noise and improving aesthetic quality. In Edinburgh, focusing Nature Network opportunities along active travel routes in nature-deprived areas offers a clear opportunity to reduce inequalities in nature exposure between neighbourhoods. These insights offer a valuable baseline for tracking changing attitudes of young people over time and for designing Nature Networks that reflect, respect and respond to the priorities and needs of urban young people.

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Authors contributions

EB and CE conceived the ideas and designed methodology; EB collected the data; EB analysed the data; EB led the writing of the manuscript. Both authors contributed critically to the drafts and gave final approval for publication.

Generative AI (Microsoft 365 Copilot with Enterprise Data Protection) was used to assist in refining text and R code during the preparation of this report. All authors made substantial contributions to the work, have thoroughly reviewed all content for accuracy, and take full responsibility for the integrity of their respective contributions.

Appendix A: Detailed methods

A.1 Data collection

Cultural background is used to explore patterns of human nature connection (Fränkel et al. 2019) and urban neighbourhood biodiversity (Kinzig et al. 2005) alongside other beliefs and behaviours (Horne et al. 2004), with the advantage of allowing participants to self-identify with a set of cultural experiences and values independent of nationality or race. In this survey we presented cultural background categories in line with familiar ethnic groupings for the region (Scotland's Census 2025).

NDVI and SIMD data were collated for 21 secondary school catchments across Edinburgh, composed of 18 non-denominational and three overlapping Roman Catholic schools with much larger catchments. Two non-denominational school catchments at the western edge of Edinburgh were excluded from this analysis due to extensive overlap with neighbouring local authorities. Our participating sample included four non-denominational schools and one Roman Catholic school. NDVI data were derived from Sentinel-2 satellite imagery at 10m resolution.

A.2 Data handling and analyses

For qualitative free-text responses, we coded data using relevant categories (e.g. wildlife taxa, green, blue or grey features, resource type) and extracted illustrative quotations to provide context. 'Green features' included references to gardens, hills, sports fields, individual trees and vegetated habitats (e.g. woods, grass, meadows etc.). 'Blue features' included references to ponds, rivers and coastal areas, while grey features included references to buildings, streets, paths and any other infrastructure. Not all participants described their mapped locations and descriptions often referred to more than one feature, meaning that sample sizes vary accordingly.

Cultural backgrounds with fewer than ten responses were combined into a single category ("other cultural backgrounds") to ensure anonymity and sufficient sample size for further analysis. As all questions were optional, response rates varied throughout the survey and summary statistics were calculated according to the sample size relevant to each question.

Geospatial data (routes and locations) from the mapping survey were combined with NDVI and SIMD datasets, and summary values extracted for different spatial scales: school catchments, data zones, home neighbourhood (100m buffer around destination from travel route), travel landscape (500m buffer around travel route) and travel experience (30m buffer around travel route; Figure 3).

Figure 3. Schematic showing location of school, mapped travel route to home environment, and buffer dimensions for spatial data handling.

We identified local indicators of spatial association between data zones across the city using Local Moran's I , identifying spatially correlated high-greenness areas (High-High), low-greenness areas (Low-Low) and boundary zones (High-Low and Low-High). The Gini Index provided insight into the statistical dispersion of equality for NDVI and SIMD. Gini ranges from 0 to 1, 0 represents perfect equality and 1 represents perfect inequality.

We used a Bayesian hierarchical framework to assess the credibility of predictors across all response variables. Age group, gender and cultural background were included as predictors in all models, with school as a grouping factor.

A.3 Limitations

This study has several limitations affecting how far the findings can be generalised. Sampling focused on mainstream secondary schools, and we did not include questions about disability and/or mobility. In addition, our emphasis on active travel excluded young people who rely on assisted or vehicular transport in our assessment of travel greenness (all participants are included in other analyses). The sample also lacked representation from the most deprived neighbourhoods in Edinburgh, limiting our ability to assess nature inequities across the full socioeconomic spectrum. Finally, small sample sizes for minority cultural backgrounds and genders constrained interpretation of subgroup differences.

There are also methodological constraints. The study relied on desk based self-reporting of locations, nature connection and value-based perceptions, which may introduce inaccuracies or recall bias. Analyses of travel routes did not capture seasonal variation or account for blue space, both of which influence exposure and perceptions of urban nature. Greenness reflects only one dimension of nature exposure, though it remains a widely used and comparable metric in urban studies. Future work could broaden analyses of young people's routine exposure and proximity to nature by incorporating additional datasets on accessible greenspaces, blue spaces, designated nature sites, connectivity, and other indicators of nature access and equity.

Finally, while our semi-quantitative methods are effective for identifying spatial patterns and associations, they provide limited insight into the underlying motivations, meanings and lived experiences that shape young people's relationships with nature. Future research incorporating participatory, qualitative, and accessibility-focused approaches would help to address these gaps and deepen understanding of how urban nature is encountered, valued and accessed by diverse groups of young people.

Appendix B: Detailed results

B.1 Summary of city and catchment-scale data

Across the City of Edinburgh, SIMD ranged from rank 11 to 6,976 (the latter representing the least deprived data zone in Scotland; Figure 4). Our sample of five school catchments demonstrated higher average SIMD than all schools (Table 1). Inequality in the distribution of SIMD ranks between all data zones was moderate (Gini SIMD = 0.27), ranging from 0.07-0.19 in our sample schools (Table 1). Greenness, measured as mean-weighted NDVI for each data zone (overall mean = 0.45), ranged across the city from <0.13 (e.g. Old Town, Princes Street & Leith Street and The Shore & Constitution Street) to >0.76 (e.g. Dalmeny, Kirkliston & Newbridge and Silverknowes & Davidson's Mains). The greenness characteristics of our sampled schools aligned closely with all secondary school catchments (Table 1). Inequality in the distribution of greenness among data zones was limited (Gini NDVI = 0.15 at the city scale and <0.21 for all school catchments) with some close to spatial equality (e.g. minimum Gini NDVI=0.06; Table 1).

Local analysis of spatial clustering identified 45% of the city into high-greenness areas, found primarily in the rural western edges of the local authority towards Queensferry (Table 1). In contrast, only 3% of the city by area was classified as low-greenness, found in the centre of the city and towards the northern coastal zones. Spatial clustering of greenness varied between schools (Table 1). Our sample contained higher-than-average shares of both high and low greenness areas (high-greenness share: 18% vs. 16% across all schools; low-greenness share: 10% vs. 5%; Table 1). There was no clear relationship between greenness (NDVI) and socioeconomic context (SIMD) among school catchments (Figure 5). However, at the data-zone scale, NDVI and SIMD showed a nonlinear association, with high greenness occurring in less deprived areas (median SIMD for high-high clusters = 6,418; IQR: 5,723–6,761) and low/average greenness spanning a wide range of SIMD ranks (median SIMD for low-low clusters = 3,412; IQR: 2,696–4,497) creating an asymmetric uneven distribution (Figure 6).

Figure 4. Map showing the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) for data zones across the City of Edinburgh (n=597). SIMD ranks range from 11 (high deprivation) to 6976 (the least deprived neighbourhood in Scotland).

Boxplots showing distribution of greenness (NDVI) and socio-economic context (SIMD) for datazones within Edinburgh secondary school catchments. Dark grey indicates schools in our sample. Datazones excluded if less than 25% crossover with school catchment.

Figure 5. Boxplots showing distribution of greenness (NDVI) and socio-economic context (SIMD) of data zones within Edinburgh secondary school catchments (n=21). Dark grey indicates schools in our sample (n=5). Data zones were excluded if less than 25% crossover with school catchment.

Figure 6. Scatter plot and boxplots showing relationship between greenness (NDVI) and socio-economic context (SIMD) of data zones across the City of Edinburgh. Spatial clustering of greenness was identified using Local Moran's I, classifying each data zone into clusters of high-greenness (HH), low-greenness (LL) and high-low or low-high boundary zones (HL or LH) based on mean weighted NDVI.

Table 1. Summary of data zones, greenness (NDVI) and multiple deprivation (SIMD) across the City of Edinburgh and secondary school catchments. This analysis compares 21 secondary schools across Edinburgh composed of 18 non-denominational and three Roman Catholic schools (the latter with much larger catchments) with our participating sample of four non-denominational schools and one Roman Catholic school. Schools are anonymised throughout.

Metric	City of Edinburgh	All Schools (n=21)	Non-Denominational Schools (n=18)	Sample Schools (n=5)
No. of Data Zones	597	59 (16 – 236)	34 (16 – 62)	81 (32 – 228)
Data Zone area (km ²)	0.44 (0.01 – 23.57)	0.44 (0.12 – 2.26)	0.44 (0.12 – 2.26)	0.23 (0.12 – 0.40)
Data Zone population	860 (258 – 3,847)	860 (760 – 980)	860 (760 – 980)	893 (863 – 964)
NDVI (weighted mean)	0.45 (0.10 – 0.78)	0.51 (0.39 – 0.65)	0.50 (0.39 – 0.65)	0.52 (0.42 – 0.62)
NDVI Gini	0.15	0.13 (0.06 – 0.20)	0.13 (0.06 – 0.20)	0.15 (0.09 – 0.20)
NDVI Gini (weighted)	0.14	0.13 (0.06 – 0.21)	0.13 (0.06 – 0.21)	0.16 (0.10 – 0.21)
SIMD (weighted mean)	4,519 (11 – 6,976)	4,420 (1,052 – 6,108)	4,359 (1,052 – 6,108)	5,525 (4,813 – 5,950)
SIMD Gini	0.26	0.26 (0.07 – 0.58)	0.26 (0.07 – 0.58)	0.15 (0.07 – 0.19)
SIMD Gini (weighted)	0.17	0.23 (0.05 – 0.55)	0.23 (0.05 – 0.55)	0.14 (0.10 – 0.20)
Share HH	0.45	0.16 (0.00 – 0.67)	0.14 (0.00 – 0.67)	0.18 (0.00 – 0.59)
Share LL	0.03	0.05 (0.00 – 0.32)	0.05 (0.00 – 0.32)	0.10 (0.00 – 0.27)
Share NS	0.51	0.77 (0.33 – 1.00)	0.79 (0.33 – 1.00)	0.69 (0.41 – 0.94)

Single-value rows show a city-wide statistic; ranged rows show *mean (min-max)* across catchments.

B.2 Summary of participant data

B.2.1 Demographics and home environments

Participants ranged from 12 to 18 years with most in the 14-16 and 12-14 age groups (57% and 38% respectively). Forty-nine percent identified as male, 43% female and 2% non-binary (with the remainder not answering). Most participants identified their cultural background as White (78%), with the remainder representing Asian (9%) and other cultural backgrounds (5%) or not answering (8%). Most participants had access to a private (65%) or shared (25%) garden and came from families owning at least one car (85%) with access to a bicycle (85%).

Self-reported nature connection ranged from 1 (low) to 7 (high), with most participants selecting mid-range values (mean = 4.11 SD = 1.38). The socioeconomic context of participants' home neighbourhoods ranged from SIMD rank 228 to 6,971 (median = 6,006, IQR = 4,538-6,689). The greenness of home neighbourhoods ranged from 0 to 0.76 (mean = 0.43 ± 0.1 SD). Participant responses are summarised in Table 2 and Table 3.

B.2.2 Travel

Two-hundred and ninety-one of our participants plotted their most recent route home from school, with 44% reporting exclusively active modes of travel – walking and/or cycling – ranging from 10% to 70% between schools. Walking was the most common active mode of travel, with only five out of 127 individuals reporting cycling in their journey. Mean distance travelled was greater for vehicular than active travel (5.66 km ± 4.39 vs 1.67 km ± 1.11). Greenness experienced by young people along their travel routes (30m buffer) ranged from NDVI 0.13 to 0.73 with an overall mean of 0.33 ± 0.11 for vehicular travel compared to 0.39 ± 0.14 for active travel.

When asked how often they travelled the mapped route, 46% of participants responded 'this is the only route I use to get home from school', 36% that 'this is the route I usually use to get home from school but I sometimes use other routes' and 9% that 'I often use other routes to get home from school'. Participants chose these routes because they were quick (53%), easy (49%), sociable (37%), pleasant (24%), safe (19%), the only option (19%), and/or cheap (14%). Compared to vehicular travel, active travel was more often described as pleasant (36% vs. 14%), sociable (48% vs. 29%), safe (29% vs. 12%), and quick (60% vs. 48%). In contrast, vehicular travellers were more likely to say they had no alternative (25% vs. 12%).

B.2.3 Feedback

66% participants agreed (moderately or strongly) that the survey was easy to complete (n = 247, NA = 58). 61% of participants agreed that they enjoyed participating in the survey (n = 236, NA = 65). 27% of participants agreed that they learnt something from participating in the survey (29% disagreed and 43% neither agreed nor disagreed; n = 229; NA = 76). 59% of participants agreed that the project will make a positive impact on their city (11% disagreed and 30% neither agreed nor disagreed; n = 226; NA = 79). 56% of participants agreed that the project will make a positive impact on our living planet (15% disagreed and 28% neither agreed nor disagreed; n = 226; NA = 79).

Table 2. Summary of participant responses by School.... part 1/2.

Variable	School					
	Overall N = 305 [†]	A N = 69 [†]	B N = 52 [†]	C N = 85 [†]	D N = 50 [†]	E N = 49 [†]
How old are you?						
12-14	114 (38%)	18 (26%)	21 (43%)	74 (87%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)
14-16	171 (57%)	50 (74%)	25 (51%)	10 (12%)	40 (80%)	46 (96%)
16-18	15 (5%)	0 (0%)	3 (6%)	1 (1%)	9 (18%)	2 (4%)
Unknown	5	1	3	0	0	1
What is your gender?						
Female	129 (43%)	29 (43%)	24 (48%)	39 (46%)	24 (50%)	13 (28%)
Male	147 (49%)	36 (54%)	20 (40%)	34 (40%)	23 (48%)	34 (72%)
Non-binary	6 (2%)	0 (0%)	2 (4%)	4 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Prefer not to say	15 (5%)	2 (3%)	4 (8%)	8 (9%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)
Unknown	8	2	2	0	2	2
What is your cultural background?						
A. White (Scottish, Other British, Irish, Gypsy/Traveller, Polish or other white ethnic group)	227 (78%)	53 (82%)	36 (72%)	61 (75%)	35 (73%)	42 (89%)
B. Mixed or multiple ethnic groups	9 (3%)	2 (3%)	2 (4%)	4 (5%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)
C. Asian, Asian Scottish, Asian British	25 (9%)	3 (5%)	9 (18%)	3 (4%)	8 (17%)	2 (4%)
D. African, African Scottish or African British	4 (1%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (4%)	0 (0%)	1 (2%)
E. Caribbean or Black, Black Scottish or Black British	2 (1%)	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (2%)
F. Other ethnic group (please state below)	13 (4%)	4 (6%)	1 (2%)	4 (5%)	3 (6%)	1 (2%)
Prefer not to say	11 (4%)	3 (5%)	1 (2%)	6 (7%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)
Unknown	14	4	2	4	2	2

Table 2 cont. Summary of participant responses by school. ... part 2/2.

Do you have access to a garden?						
No	30 (10%)	3 (4%)	10 (20%)	11 (13%)	3 (6%)	3 (6%)
Yes - private garden	195 (65%)	47 (69%)	22 (44%)	48 (56%)	35 (70%)	43 (90%)
Yes - shared garden	76 (25%)	18 (26%)	18 (36%)	26 (31%)	12 (24%)	2 (4%)
Unknown	4	1	2	0	0	1
Does your family own a car?						
No	46 (15%)	6 (9%)	12 (24%)	22 (26%)	4 (8%)	2 (4%)
Yes 1+	253 (85%)	61 (91%)	38 (76%)	63 (74%)	46 (92%)	45 (96%)
Unknown	6	2	2	0	0	2
Do you have access to a bike?						
No	46 (15%)	12 (18%)	11 (22%)	13 (15%)	7 (14%)	3 (6%)
Yes - I have a shared bike	17 (6%)	4 (6%)	1 (2%)	6 (7%)	3 (6%)	3 (6%)
Yes - I have my own bike	234 (79%)	51 (76%)	37 (76%)	65 (77%)	40 (80%)	41 (87%)
Unknown	8	2	3	1	0	2
How did you travel home from school?						
Active Travel	129 (44%)	34 (51%)	31 (67%)	27 (33%)	5 (10%)	32 (70%)
Vehicular Travel	162 (56%)	33 (49%)	15 (33%)	55 (67%)	45 (90%)	14 (30%)
Unknown	14	2	6	3	0	3
Nature Connection (mean ± SD)						
	4.11 ± 1.38	4.03 ± 1.22	4.20 ± 1.54	4.28 ± 1.38	3.84 ± 1.35	4.13 ± 1.44
Unknown	7	1	2	2	0	2
Home SIMD (median [IQR])						
	6,006 [4,538, 6,689]	6,662 [6,437, 6,816]	4,953 [2,801, 5,778]	5,860 [4,593, 6,648]	5,206 [2,271, 6,467]	6,440 [5,365, 6,845]
Unknown	14	2	6	3	0	3
Home NDVI (mean ± SD)						
	0.43 ± 0.12	0.43 ± 0.11	0.38 ± 0.13	0.41 ± 0.11	0.41 ± 0.12	0.51 ± 0.10
Unknown	14	2	6	3	0	3
† n (%); Mean ± SD; Median [Q1, Q3]						

Table 3. Summary of participant responses by demography, nature connection and home environment (n=305).

Variable	Group	n	Nature Connection (mean ± SD)	SIMD (median [IQR])	NDVI (mean ± SD)
Age	12-14	113	4.30 ± 1.37	5926 [IQR 4596–6638]	0.42 ± 0.11
Age	14-16	170	4.01 ± 1.34	6389 [IQR 4948–6699]	0.44 ± 0.12
Age	16-18	14	4.00 ± 1.75	3755 [IQR 2441–5846]	0.36 ± 0.13
Age	NA	1	2.00 ± NA	4569 [IQR 4569–4569]	0.16 ± NA
Gender	Female	128	4.12 ± 1.41	5907 [IQR 4018–6658]	0.43 ± 0.11
Gender	Male	145	4.12 ± 1.36	6274 [IQR 4957–6701]	0.43 ± 0.13
Gender	Non-binary	6	4.50 ± 1.76	5439 [IQR 4887–6400]	0.38 ± 0.13
Gender	NA	19	3.79 ± 1.18	4948 [IQR 3612–6248]	0.38 ± 0.11
Cultural Background	Asian	25	4.12 ± 1.64	4846 [IQR 2470–6408]	0.37 ± 0.13
Cultural Background	Other ethnic group	28	3.82 ± 1.33	5406 [IQR 2910–6549]	0.42 ± 0.11
Cultural Background	White	224	4.16 ± 1.36	6305 [IQR 4908–6699]	0.44 ± 0.12
Cultural Background	NA	21	4.00 ± 1.30	5576 [IQR 4476–6491]	0.39 ± 0.13
Garden Access	No	30	3.90 ± 1.79	4953 [IQR 2882–6118]	0.36 ± 0.12
Garden Access	Yes - private garden	193	4.08 ± 1.36	6305 [IQR 4818–6699]	0.45 ± 0.12
Garden Access	Yes - shared garden	75	4.27 ± 1.22	5762 [IQR 4432–6742]	0.40 ± 0.11
Garden Access	NA	0	NA ± NA	4569 [IQR 4569–4569]	0.16 ± NA
SIMD (home)	Q1	73	3.99 ± 1.49	2566 [IQR 1582–3464]	0.37 ± 0.13
SIMD (home)	Q4	72	4.31 ± 1.39	6862 [IQR 6784–6919]	0.44 ± 0.09
NDVI (home)	Q1	73	3.96 ± 1.53	5045 [IQR 2923–6638]	0.27 ± 0.07
NDVI (home)	Q4	73	4.34 ± 1.39	6416 [IQR 5728–6699]	0.57 ± 0.05

B.3 Routine exposure to nature

Landscape-scale greenness (500m buffer) was the strongest predictor of greenness experienced by young people along their active travel routes. Each one-SD increase in landscape NDVI was associated with a ~ 0.08 increase in route-level NDVI (95% CrI 0.05–0.12). Cultural background was also associated with greenness along active travel routes; compared to White or Asian participants from other cultural backgrounds experienced higher route-level NDVI by ~ 0.05 (95% CrI 0.02–0.09).

There was no credible evidence that home environment (NDVI or SIMD), route-level SIMD, or the remaining individual characteristics (nature connection, age category, or gender) were meaningfully associated with route-level greenness in this sample (Figure 7). However, a sensitivity test estimating the normalised difference of route and landscape-scale greenness indicated slightly stronger evidence for an association with gender, with Females experiencing ~ 0.05 lower NDVI compared to Males (95% CrI -0.092 to -0.003). The direction and certainty of associations between predictors and response variables for all models are summarised in Figure 1.

The relationship between predicted route-level and landscape-scale NDVI showed that, on average, young people travelled along routes that were less green than the surrounding areas available to them (Figure 6B). 95% Credible Intervals indicated that this relationship was reliably different to a 1:1 relationship for landscapes with mean NDVI greater than 0.4 (Figure 7B).

Spatial heterogeneity and random effects suggested that individual and structural factors beyond those predictors considered may also shape travel greenness exposure.

Figure 7. A. Predictors of experienced route-level greenness (NDVI; Beta regression with logit link); effects shown on the response scale with 95% Credible Intervals. B. Relationship between landscape-scale greenness (500m buffer around travel route) and route-level greenness (30m buffer around travel route), averaged over all covariates. Grey ribbon indicates 95% Credible intervals, and the dashed line indicates a hypothetical 1:1 relationship. NDVI = Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (satellite-derived greenness); SIMD = Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation

B.4 Recognising the dis(benefits) of nature

B.4.1 Mixed methods summaries

Wildlife - 195 participants collectively identified 387 ‘good places to see wildlife’ across the city. The number of wildlife locations mapped per participant ranged from 0 to 11 (median = 1, mean = 1.27 ± 1.53). Green features dominated these descriptions (217 responses from 135 participants, e.g., parks, woods, hills, gardens and cemeteries), followed by blue (93 responses from 69 participants, e.g. rivers, canals and coastal) and grey features (41 responses from 33 participants, e.g. buildings, streets and paths).

For participants who mapped at least one wildlife location, the number of unique broad taxonomic groups reported per person ranged from 0 to 7 (median = 2; mean = 2.04 ± 1.31). The most common taxonomic groups reported were birds (197 responses from 127 participants), mammals (152 responses from 99 participants) and plants (140 responses from 88 participants). Participants also reported good places to see invertebrates (33 responses), fish (14 responses), amphibians (7 responses) and fungi (1 response).

Specific mammal taxa identified included foxes, squirrels, rabbits, otters, seals, badgers, mice and weasels. Bird taxa identified included gulls, swans, ducks, herons, geese, pigeons, bullfinches, collared doves, buzzards, robins and woodpeckers. Plant taxa usually referenced broad groups (trees, grasses, brambles etc.) but some species or genus-level names were also given, including nettles, wild garlic, gorse, snowdrop, and daffodil.

Resources - 127 participants identified 165 locations where they could ‘get things from nature’ ranging from 0 to 5 locations per participant (median = 0, mean = 0.54 ± 0.79). Green features were most reported (81 responses from 77 participants), followed by blue (17 responses from 15 participants) and grey features (18 responses from 18 participants).

Information provided by participants showed that the most common resources collected were those for play and/or decoration, such as sticks, conkers, cones, leaves, and seashells (55 responses from 49 participants), followed by wild food such as berries and tree nuts (36 responses from 31 participants). Other participants described locations where they could get photos and/or a good view (5 responses) or a restorative experience, such as fresh air (15 responses), demonstrating an alternative interpretation of the question. The described locations were primarily green (87 responses from 73 participants), with some blue (14 responses from 11 participants) and grey spaces (16 responses from 14 participants).

Important natural places - 138 participants mapped 217 natural places that were important to them, ranging from 0 to 7 locations per participant (median = 0, mean = 0.71 ± 1.04). Green features were most described (104 responses from 81 participants), followed by grey (22 responses from 20 participants) and blue features (20 responses from 19 participants). The most common reasons given related to beauty or inspiration (90 responses, 70 participants), improved mental health (81 responses, 80 participants), leisure (80 responses, 63 participants) and improved physical health (59 responses, 42 participants). Those participants who gave additional information beyond the provided categories shared that these natural places were important to them because they had sentimental / nostalgic value (15 responses, 12 participants), they spend time there with their friends (12 responses, 11 participants), they walk there (alone or with family / dog; 12 responses, 10 participants) or they play sport there (6 responses, 4 participants).

Bothersome natural places – 53 participants mapped 63 natural places that bothered them, ranging from 0 to 2 locations per participant (median = 0, mean = 0.21 ± 0.48). Green features were most described (22 responses from 20 participants), followed by grey (15 responses from 15 participants) and blue features (2 responses from 2 respondents). Reasons given for why these sites cause concern included that they were dirty and/or littered (11 responses, 11 participants), there were safety issues (8 responses, 8 participants), the participants didn't like the mud (7 responses) or getting stung / jagged (5 responses).

B.4.2 Modelling summaries

Positive natural locations - We found strong evidence that self-reported nature connection and gender were associated with the number of positive natural locations (wildlife, resources, and important locations) mapped in our study, with mixed evidence for cultural background (Figure 1).

The expected count of wildlife locations per respondent was ~1.05 (95% CrI 0.65–1.73) for the reference profile (Location = Wildlife; Age = 12–14; Gender = Male; Cultural background = White; continuous predictors at their mean). Participants mapped ~44% fewer important natural locations compared to wildlife locations (IRR = 0.56, 95% CrI: 0.46–0.68) and 56% fewer natural resource locations (IRR = 0.44, 0.36–0.54).

Participants with stronger nature connection mapped ~36% more locations per one-SD increase in nature connection score (IRR = 1.36, 1.22–1.52). Females mapped 36% more locations than males (IRR = 1.36, 1.09–1.68). Compared to White participants, participants from Asian and other cultural backgrounds mapped ~32% fewer natural locations (IRR [Asian] = 0.68, 0.44–1.03; IRR [Other] = 0.68, 0.46–0.98). Associations with home NDVI, home SIMD, route NDVI and age were small and/or uncertain.

Wildlife taxa - Self-reported nature connection showed a clear positive association with overall number of wildlife taxa reported by young people at mapped wildlife locations, whereas demographic, home environment, and route predictors had relatively limited explanatory power (Figure 1).

For each one-SD increase in nature connection, participant reporting increased by 19%, from ~2 to ~2.2 taxa for the reference profile (IRR = 1.19, 95% CrI: 1.06–1.32). Effects for other predictors were small and/or uncertain: Females reported higher taxonomic richness than males (IRR = 1.21, 0.98–1.51), and participants from Asian and other cultural backgrounds reported fewer taxa than those from White cultural backgrounds, though estimates were imprecise (IRR [Asian] = 0.68, 0.39–1.10; IRR [Other] = 0.84, 0.53–1.27). Age differences were small, and the effects of NDVI and SIMD at home and NDVI along routes were negligible.

Bothersome natural locations - We found a clear positive association between the likelihood of reporting any bothersome natural locations and the SIMD rank of their home neighbourhoods, and a positive but uncertain association with cultural background (Figure 1).

A one-SD increase in home SIMD (indicating less deprivation) was associated with 55% higher odds of reporting any bothersome natural locations, increasing baseline probability from ~0.15 to ~0.23 (OR = 1.55, 95% CrI: 1.05–2.36). Participants identifying as Asian or from other cultural backgrounds also had higher odds of reporting bothersome locations than White participants, though estimates were imprecise (OR [Asian] = 1.49, 0.68–3.22; OR [Other] = 1.46, 0.70–2.95). Effects for self-reported nature connection, gender, age, and greenness of home and route environments were small and/or uncertain.

B.5 Recognising ecosystem (dis)services and places for improvements

B.5.1 Mixed methods summary

Across all categories, 181 participants mapped 671 locations they felt needed improving across the city. The number and distribution of mapped locations within each category — poor air quality, poor water quality, noisy, hot, flood prone, and ugly — are summarised in Table 4.

61 participants mapped an additional 75 locations needing ‘other’ improvements. Common explanations included insufficient or poor-quality nature or greenspace (n = 15), anthropogenic waste such as litter or fly tipping (n = 9), traffic and road issues (n = 9), safety concerns (n = 4), and bad smells (n = 4). Less frequently mentioned reasons included areas being too busy or too dark, references to specific neighbourhoods or local infrastructure (e.g. schools and housing), poor accessibility, and a lack of facilities such as shops or phone signal. Some participants also referred to issues already captured in previous mapping categories, including flooding (n = 3), poor water quality (n = 2), locations considered too ugly (n = 8), and places described as too noisy (n = 2).

B.5.2 Modelling summary

We found no strong evidence that individual level predictors — self reported nature connection, home or route environment, or demographic characteristics — explained variation in the overall number of locations mapped as needing improvement (Figure 1). Location type effects were pronounced relative to the *poor air quality* reference: number of locations mapped per participant were credibly higher for places considered too noisy (IRR = 1.45, 95% CrI: 1.09–1.91) and too ugly (IRR = 1.52, 1.15–1.99), and lower for locations considered too hot (IRR = 0.33, 0.23–0.48), or having poor water quality (IRR = 0.60, 0.43–0.84). Estimated effects for all other predictors were generally small and imprecise (wide 95% credible intervals).

Table 4. Locations mapped by participants that they felt needed improvements across the city (n=305 participants). NB/ We detected six responses with unrealistically high click-rates given the time available (36 to 404 locations mapped per person per category). We removed these anomalous data by imposing a cap of 30 mapped locations per individual per category and will review this element of the methodology in future surveys.

CATEGORY	PARTICIPANTS MAPPING ≥ 1 LOCATION	LOCATIONS MAPPED	MEDIAN (RANGE)	MEAN \pm SD	NOTES
ALL	181	671	1 (0–23)	2.2 \pm 3.14	—
POOR WATER QUALITY	56	89	0 (0–22)	0.30 \pm 1.35	One response >30 excluded
POOR AIR QUALITY	96	141	0 (0–11)	0.46 \pm 0.99	—
TOO NOISY	131	193	0 (0–7)	0.63 \pm 1.02	—
TOO HOT	44	49	0 (0–2)	0.16 \pm 0.41	—
FLOOD-PRONE	82	113	0 (0–11)	0.37 \pm 1.01	—
UGLY	102	204	0 (0–12)	0.67 \pm 1.45	Five responses >30 excluded
OTHER	61	75	0 (0–4)	0.25 \pm 0.55	—

References

- Aggio, Daniel, Lee Smith, Abi Fisher, and Mark Hamer. 2015. 'Mothers' Perceived Proximity to Green Space Is Associated with TV Viewing Time in Children: The Growing Up in Scotland Study'. *Preventive Medicine* 70 (January): 46–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2014.11.018>.
- Alderton, Amanda, Karen Villanueva, Meredith O'Connor, Claire Boulangé, and Hannah Badland. 2019. 'Reducing Inequities in Early Childhood Mental Health: How Might the Neighborhood Built Environment Help Close the Gap? A Systematic Search and Critical Review'. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 16 (9): 1516. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16091516>.
- Bornioli, Anna, Aife Hopkins-Doyle, Fabio Fasoli, et al. 2024. 'Sex and the City Park: The Role of Gender and Sex in Psychological Restoration in Urban Greenspaces'. *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 100 (December): 102476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2024.102476>.
- Burns, F., S. Mordue, N. al Fulaij, et al. 2023. *State of Nature 2023*. September. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20636.26245>.
- Chawla, Louise. 2015. 'Benefits of Nature Contact for Children'. *Journal of Planning Literature* 30 (4): 433–52. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0885412215595441>.
- Chawla, Louise. 2020. 'Childhood Nature Connection and Constructive Hope: A Review of Research on Connecting with Nature and Coping with Environmental Loss'. *People and Nature* 2 (3): 619–42. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10128>.
- City of Edinburgh Council. 2020. 'Briefing Note – Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation, 2020'. <https://www.edinburgh.gov.uk/downloads/file/29520/social-index-of-multiple-deprivation-simd-report>.
- City of Edinburgh Council. 2024. *Edinburgh by Numbers 2024*. <https://www.edinburgh.gov.uk/downloads/file/30669/edinburgh-by-numbers-2024>.
- Cole, Stuart, Jessica Goodenough, Melissa Haniff, et al. 2024. 'GreenSpace & Us: Exploring Co-Design Approaches to Increase Engagement with Nature by Girls and Young Women'. *Gateways: International Journal of Community Research and Engagement* 17 (1). <https://doi.org/10.5130/ijcre.v17i1.8881>.
- Collins, Melissa A., Valeria Fike Romero, Aujanèe Young, et al. 2025. 'The Value of Outdoor Environmental Education Programs for Girls and Youth of Color: Cultivating Positive Dispositions toward Science and the Environment'. *Environmental Education Research* 31 (1): 108–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2024.2340502>.
- Das, Dillip Kumar. 2025. 'Exploring the Intersection of Environmental Justice and Urban Green Space Planning: A Systematic Review'. *Urban Science* 9 (12): 540. <https://doi.org/10.3390/urbansci9120540>.
- EcoCo. 2019. 'Ecological Coherence: A Practitioners' Guide'. <https://inner-forth-futures.s3.eu-west->

2.amazonaws.com/files/EcologicalCoherencePractitionersGuide_07022019_FINAL_spreads.pdf.

- Edinburgh Living Landscapes. n.d. *Edinburgh Nature Network*.
<https://edinburghlivinglandscape.org.uk/project/edinburgh-nature-network/>.
- Everyone's Environment. 2025. 'Making Environmental Policy Inclusive In Scotland'.
<https://www.ercs.scot/wp/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/Making-environmental-policy-inclusive-in-Scotland.pdf>.
- Fränkel, Silvia, Daniela Sellmann-Risse, and Melanie Basten. 2019. 'Fourth Graders' Connectedness to Nature - Does Cultural Background Matter?' *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 66 (December): 101347.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2019.101347>.
- Gentin, Sandra, Kati Pitkänen, Anna Maria Chondromatidou, Søren Præsthholm, Ann Dolling, and Anna Maria Palsdottir. 2019. 'Nature-Based Integration of Immigrants in Europe: A Review'. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 43 (July): 126379.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2019.126379>.
- Hagemann, Frederik Aagaard, Åsa Ode Sang, and Thomas Barfoed Randrup. 2024. 'Young People's Participation in Urban Landscape Planning and Transformation: A Scoping Review of Interactive Approaches'. *Socio-Ecological Practice Research* 6 (4): 433–54. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42532-024-00200-1>.
- Horne, Robert, Lída Graupner, Susie Frost, John Weinman, Siobhan Melanie Wright, and Matthew Hankins. 2004. 'Medicine in a Multi-Cultural Society: The Effect of Cultural Background on Beliefs about Medications'. *Social Science & Medicine* 59 (6): 1307–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2004.01.009>.
- Horton, John. 2017. 'Disabilities, Urban Natures and Children's Outdoor Play'. *Social & Cultural Geography* 18 (8): 1152–74.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14649365.2016.1245772>.
- IPBES. 2019. *Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6417333>.
- Jack, Gordon. 2010. 'Place Matters: The Significance of Place Attachments for Children's Well-Being'. *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (3): 755–71.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/bjsw/bcn142>.
- Jaffe, Julia, and Janet Loebach. 2024. 'Fostering Youth-Enabling Environments: A Participatory Affordance-Capability Framework for the Development and Use of Youth-Engaged Environmental Assessments'. *Youth & Society* 56 (1): 164–92.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118X221145713>.
- Kinzig, Ann P., Paige Warren, Chris Martin, Diane Hope, and Madhusudan Katti. 2005. 'The Effects of Human Socioeconomic Status and Cultural Characteristics on Urban Patterns of Biodiversity'. *Ecology and Society* 10 (1).
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/26267712>.
- Knudsen, Line, Holman Eleanor, Bradshaw Paul, et al. 2025. *Life at Age 17: Initial Findings from the Growing Up in Scotland Study (Sweep 11)*. Scottish Government.

<https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/research-and-analysis/2025/10/life-age-17-initial-findings-growing-up-scotland-study-sweep-11/documents/life-age-17-initial-findings-growing-up-scotland-study-sweep-11/life-age-17-initial-findings-growing-up-scotland-study-sweep-11/govscot%3Adocument/life-age-17-initial-findings-growing-up-scotland-study-sweep-11.pdf>.

Lieberman, Lauren J., Pamela Haibach-Beach, Melanie Perreault, and Alex Stribing. 2023. 'Outdoor Recreation Experiences in Youth with Visual Impairments: A Qualitative Inquiry'. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning* 23 (2): 170–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2021.1984965>.

Madera, Francesco, Martina Olcese, and Laura Migliorini. 2024. 'A Systematic Review of Nature Connectedness in Adolescents and Young Adults: Fostering Environmental Responsibility and Sustainable Practices'. *Journal of Prevention & Intervention in the Community* 52 (3–4): 400–434. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10852352.2025.2474909>.

Martin, Christian, and Sandor Czellar. 2016. 'The Extended Inclusion of Nature in Self Scale'. *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 47 (September): 181–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2016.05.006>.

McCracken, Deborah S., Deonie A. Allen, and Alan J. Gow. 2016. 'Associations between Urban Greenspace and Health-Related Quality of Life in Children'. *Preventive Medicine Reports* 3 (June): 211–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2016.01.013>.

McCrorie, Paul, Rich Mitchell, Laura Macdonald, et al. 2020. 'The Relationship between Living in Urban and Rural Areas of Scotland and Children's Physical Activity and Sedentary Levels: A Country-Wide Cross-Sectional Analysis'. *BMC Public Health* 20 (1): 304. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-8311-y>.

Miller, James R. 2005. 'Biodiversity Conservation and the Extinction of Experience'. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 20 (8): 430–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2005.05.013>.

National Records of Scotland. 2024. 'Mid-2024 Population Estimates'. <https://www.nrscotland.gov.uk/publications/mid-2024-population-estimates/>.

NatureScot. 2024. 'A Framework for Nature Networks in Scotland'. <https://www.nature.scot/doc/nature-networks-framework#The+current+picture+in+Scotland>.

NatureScot. 2025a. 'Ecosystem Services - Nature's Benefits'. <https://www.nature.scot/scotlands-biodiversity/scottish-biodiversity-strategy/ecosystem-approach/ecosystem-services-natures-benefits>.

NatureScot. 2025b. 'NatureScot and Youth Engagement'. <https://www.nature.scot/professional-advice/young-people-learning-outdoors-and-developing-skills/naturescot-and-youth-engagement>.

Newton, Dillon, Mariam Zarjoo, John Stephenson, and Philip Brown. 2026. 'Impact of Residential Green Spaces on Health Inequalities in the UK: A Systematic Review and Exploratory Meta-Analysis'. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 118 (April): 129304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2026.129304>.

- Olcese, Martina, Francesco Madera, Paola Cardinali, and Laura Migliorini. 2026. 'Contact with Nature and Youth Well-Being: Insights from Natural and Urban Contexts'. *Current Opinion in Psychology* 67 (February): 102199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsy.2025.102199>.
- Olsen, Jonathan R., Fiona M. Caryl, Paul McCrorie, and Richard Mitchell. 2022. 'Socioeconomic Inequality in Scottish Children's Exposure to and Use of Natural Space and Private Gardens, Measured by GPS'. *Landscape and Urban Planning* 223 (July): 104425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2022.104425>.
- Olsen, Jonathan R., Kevin Y. K. Leung, Natalie Nicholls, and Becky P. Y. Loo. 2021. 'Do Neighbourhood Characteristics Matter in Understanding School Children's Active Lifestyles? A Cross-Region Multi-City Comparison of Glasgow, Edinburgh and Hong Kong'. *Children's Geographies* 19 (4): 488–504. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14733285.2020.1828826>.
- Pakeman, Robin J., Antonia Eastwood, Dominic Duckett, Kerry A. Waylen, Jon Hopkins, and David M. Bailey. 2023. *Understanding the Indirect Drivers of Biodiversity Loss in Scotland*. NatureScot. <https://www.nature.scot/doc/naturescot-research-report-1309-understanding-indirect-drivers-biodiversity-loss-scotland>.
- Pia, Nazmun Akter, and Karabi Bezboruah. 2025. 'Urban Design Strategies for Creating Child-Friendly Neighborhoods: A Systematic Literature Review'. *Cities* 162 (July): 105919. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2025.105919>.
- Richardson, Elizabeth A., Jamie Pearce, Niamh K. Shortt, and Richard Mitchell. 2017. 'The Role of Public and Private Natural Space in Children's Social, Emotional and Behavioural Development in Scotland: A Longitudinal Study'. *Environmental Research* 158 (October): 729–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.07.038>.
- Richardson, Miles, Anne Hunt, Joe Hinds, et al. 2019. 'A Measure of Nature Connectedness for Children and Adults: Validation, Performance, and Insights'. *Sustainability* 11 (12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11123250>.
- Roberts, Michaela, Katherine N. Irvine, and Alistair McVittie. 2021. 'Associations between Greenspace and Mental Health Prescription Rates in Urban Areas'. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 64 (September): 127301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2021.127301>.
- Schmidt, Jenne. 2023. 'Crippling Environmental Education: Rethinking Disability, Nature, and Interdependent Futures'. *Australian Journal of Environmental Education* 39 (2): 251–68. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aee.2022.26>.
- Scotland's Census. 2025. 'Scotland's Census at a Glance: Ethnic Groups'. <https://www.scotlandscensus.gov.uk/census-results/at-a-glance/ethnicity/>.
- Scottish Government. 2021. 'Rural Scotland Key Facts 2021'. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/rural-scotland-key-facts-2021/>.
- Stanworth, Anna, Kelvin S. H. Peh, and Rebecca J. Morris. 2024. 'Linking Network Ecology and Ecosystem Services to Benefit People'. *People and Nature* 6 (3): 1048–59. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10632>.

Sun, Yan, Somidh Saha, Heike Tost, Xiangqi Kong, and Chengyang Xu. 2022. 'Literature Review Reveals a Global Access Inequity to Urban Green Spaces'. *Sustainability* 14 (3): 1062. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031062>.

Thriving Greenspaces. n.d. 'Wilding Wee Spaces'. Thriving Greenspaces, City of Edinburgh Council. UK. <https://www.thrivinggreenspaces.scot/project/wilding-wee-spaces>.

Van Heel, Bernadette F., Riyan J. G. Van Den Born, and Noelle Aarts. 2023. 'Nature Experiences in Childhood as a Driver of Connectedness with Nature and Action for Nature: A Review'. *Ecopsychology* 15 (4): 354–67. <https://doi.org/10.1089/eco.2022.0080>.

Waite, Sue, Fatima Husain, Berenice Scandone, Emma Forsyth, and Hannah Piggott. 2023. "It's Not for People like (Them)": Structural and Cultural Barriers to Children and Young People Engaging with Nature Outside Schooling'. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning* 23 (1): 54–73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2021.1935286>.

Wesley Schultz, P. 2001. 'THE STRUCTURE OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONCERN: CONCERN FOR SELF, OTHER PEOPLE, AND THE BIOSPHERE'. *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 21 (4): 327–39. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jevp.2001.0227>.

Willberg, Elias, Christoph Fink, Robert Klein, Roope Heinonen, and Tuuli Toivonen. 2024. "Green or Short: Choose One" - A Comparison of Walking Accessibility and Greenery in 43 European Cities'. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* 113 (October): 102168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2024.102168>.